

FEATURES AND DIFFICULTIES OF TRANSLATING FOREIGN LITERATURE INTO KAZAKH

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Annotatsiya. *Chet el adabiyotining qozoq tiliga tarjimasini milliy madaniyatni boyitish va qozoq o'quvchilarining dunyoqarashini kengaytirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Biroq, bu jarayon bir qator lingvistik, madaniy va uslubiy qiyinchiliklar bilan birga keladi. Maqolada qozoq tiliga badiiy tarjimaning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi, shuningdek tarjimonlar duch keladigan odatiy muammolar tahlil qilinadi. Idiomalar, stilistik xususiyatlar va madaniy haqiqatlarni uzatishning aniq misollari keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *adabiyot, stilistika, badiiy adabiyot, o'quvchilar, janrlar.*

Аннотация. *Перевод иностранной литературы на казахский язык играет важную роль в обогащении национальной культуры и расширении кругозора казахских читателей. Однако этот процесс сопровождается рядом языковых, культурных и стилистических трудностей. В статье рассматриваются особенности художественного перевода на казахский язык, а также анализируются типичные проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются переводчики. Приводятся конкретные примеры передачи идиом, стилистических особенностей и культурных реалий.*

Ключевые слова: *литература, стилстика, художественная литература, читатели, жанры.*

Abstract. *The translation of foreign literature into Kazakh plays a vital role in enriching national culture and broadening the worldview of Kazakh readers. However, the process involves various linguistic, cultural, and stylistic challenges. This article explores the main features of literary translation into Kazakh and analyzes common difficulties encountered by translators. Through specific examples, it examines issues of linguistic equivalence, idiomatic expression, and stylistic adaptation.*

Keywords: *Literary translation, Kazakh language, cultural adaptation, equivalence, translation difficulties.*

The translation of fiction is one of the most important aspects of intercultural communication, contributing to mutual understanding between peoples and the expansion of cultural horizons. The translation of foreign literature into Kazakh is of particular importance in the context of globalization and modernization of national consciousness. Through the translation of world works, Kazakh readers have the opportunity to get acquainted with spiritual values, philosophical concepts, historical events and aesthetic traditions of other nations. However, the translation process is not just a mechanical transfer of text from one language to another. This is a creative act that requires a deep understanding of not only the language, but also the culture, mentality, and stylistic features of the original.

The Kazakh language, being Turkic in origin, has a unique grammatical and lexical structure, different from many Western European languages such as English, French, German and others. This creates certain difficulties in conveying meanings, especially when it comes to a

literary text saturated with metaphors, allusions, idiomatic expressions and nationally specific realities. In addition to linguistic differences, the translator faces problems of cultural adaptation: it is necessary to preserve the author's intention, the emotional coloring of the text and at the same time make it understandable to the Kazakh-speaking reader without distorting the original meaning.

In addition, the difference in literary traditions has a significant impact. For example, Western literature may rely on other genre canons, compositional structures, or philosophical categories that are unusual for Kazakh literature. Therefore, a translator should not only be an expert in the language, but also a cultural mediator who is able to find a balance between fidelity to the original and naturalness of sound in the Kazakh language.

This article examines the main features and difficulties faced by translators when adapting foreign fiction into the Kazakh language. Typical translation problems are analyzed, examples from well-known works are offered, and possible strategies for overcoming them are discussed. The relevance of the topic is due to the need for further development of Kazakh literature, as well as improving the quality and quantity of literary translations available to a wide readership.

1. Linguistic specifics: grammar and syntax

The Kazakh language, as a representative of the Turkic language family, is characterized by a high degree of agglutination — each grammatical form is expressed through the successive addition of affixes. This is in sharp contrast to analytical languages (English, French), in which grammatical information is conveyed more often using official words and word order.

Example:

“He has been working for three years.”

is translated into Kazakh not literally, but through reformulation:

“Ol ush zhyldan beri zhumys istep zhur.”

The arrangement of the sentence members also differs: in English, the standard order is SVO (subject + predicate + complement), in Kazakh it is SOV (subject + complement + predicate), which requires a restructuring of the entire syntactic scheme during translation.

2. Lexical and semantic difficulties

In some cases, translators are faced with the lack of exact equivalents in the Kazakh language, especially when transmitting concepts related to Western culture, jurisprudence, philosophy or everyday life.

Example:

The English word “privacy” does not have a full analogue in the Kazakh language and can be translated as “zheke kenistik”, “zheke omirdin kupiyalygy” — which requires explanation and context.

Difficulties also arise when transmitting emotionally colored words. For example, the word “melancholy” has a poetic connotation in English and may require additional expressive means when translating: “munly kuy”, “kunilsizdik”.

3. Idioms, phraseological units and wordplay

One of the main challenges is the translation of stable expressions that cannot be translated verbatim. Idioms require either a search for analogues or a descriptive translation.

Examples:

The original (English) Possible translation of (kaz.)

"Spill the beans" "Syryn ashu", "Barin aityp koyu"

"To beat around the bush" "Tikeley aitpau", "Aynaldyryp soyleu"

“The ball is in your court” “Endi sheshim sende”

Wordplay, especially in humorous and children's works (for example, books by Lewis Carroll), is almost impossible to translate verbatim. In these cases, the translator has to invent new puns, which requires not only knowledge of the language, but also creative thinking.

4. Cultural realities and concepts

There are often elements in the literature that are deeply rooted in the culture of the source: names of dishes, customs, religious terms, forms of address, social norms. A direct translation may be incomprehensible to a Kazakh reader.

Example:

The English “Thanksgiving dinner” has no exact counterpart. The following options are possible:

Descriptive translation: “rizashylyk meiramyndagi keshki as”;

adaptation: “merekelik keshki as”, if the context does not require details.

Strategies for translating realities:

Transliteration with explanation: “safari” → sayahat (safari);

Adaptation to the Kazakh culture (if allowed): “pub” → “askhana”, “cafe”;

Leaving the original with a footnote or a note.

5. Stylistics and genre specifics

Each literary work carries a unique style of the author: from laconic prose to metaphorical poetry. When translating, it is important not only to convey the meaning, but also to maintain the rhythm, intonation, and mood.

Poetic translation, especially from Old English, requires the use of poetic forms of Kazakh literature — mysal, terme, zhyr.

Example:

Shakespeare's sonnets, built on strict rhythm and rhyme, lose their shape when translated, and the translator has to choose between form and content. Some translators (for example, Satybaldy Narymbetov) resort to free translation, preserving the general idea, but adapting it to the Kazakh rhythm.

6. The role of the translator as a mediator

In the translation of fiction, the figure of the translator as an intermediary between two cultures is especially important. He doesn't just transfer words — he recreates a whole cultural layer. In some cases, the translator has to consciously move away from the original in order to preserve the emotional impact.

Example:

Minimalism prevails in the works of Ernest Hemingway. The translator needs to resist the temptation to “decorate” the text in the Kazakh version, because the author's style is a key element of artistic value.

The translation of foreign fiction into Kazakh is a complex and multifaceted process that combines linguistic, cultural and artistic aspects. The Kazakh language, with its unique grammar, stylistics and poetic tradition, requires not just formal conformity to the original, but a deep adaptation of the content, taking into account the national mentality and linguistic norms.

As the analysis shows, the main difficulties of translation lie in the transmission of idiomatic expressions, cultural realities, stylistic features of the author and the genre of the text. The translator acts not just as a linguist, but as a cultural mediator, whose task is to preserve the artistic and emotional value of the work. Successful translation requires not only excellent

command of both languages, but also literary taste, interpretive skills, creativity, and in-depth knowledge of the cultural context.

The relevance of this topic is especially great in the context of the growing need for high-quality Kazakh-language translations of classical and modern literature. Improving translation techniques, raising the professional level of translators and supporting literary translation at the state level are important conditions for the development of Kazakh literature and strengthening cultural ties with the international community.

USED LITERATURE

1. Abduali Kaidar. Kazak tili zhane audarma theory. Almaty: Gylym Publ., 1998.
2. Aldasheva A.M. Korkem audarma: the theory of money. Almaty: Rarity, 2007.
3. Newmark, Peter. A Textbook of Translation. – London: Prentice Hall, 1988.
4. Baker, Mona. In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation. – London: Routledge, 2011.
5. Baskakov N. A. Turkic languages and problems of Translation, Moscow: Nauka Publ., 1982.